

ISic3022

I.Sicily inscription 3022

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

altar

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2008.09.28 (observed)

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Camarina

Place of origin (modern)

Kamarina

Provenance

Necropolis of Passo Marinaro

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Camerina, Museo Archeologico
Regionale di Kamarina

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332343

1. σωφροσύνην τιμῶσα
2. δικαιοσύνην τε σέβου[σ]α |
3. [Ι]ππῶ ἐν ἡλικίαι πνεῦμ' ἔ[λ]ιπεν βίότου.
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645378

EDCS 70900799

PHI 332343

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 42.0848

Lavore, V. 1985. Lettura e problematica di un'epigrafe greca proveniente da una necropoli di Camarina. *Il "Gulli e*

Pennisi" (1885-1985). Acireale. pp. 217-228.

Guarducci, M. 1987. L'epigrafia greca dalle origini al tardo impero. Rome. At 404 no.11 fig.132

Brugnone, A. 1988-1989. Epigrafia greca. *Kokalos*. 34-35: 337-365. At 354-355

Di Stefano, G. 1998. Il Museo di Camarina. *Sicilia Archeologica*. 31: 209-231. At 229 fig.27 (cf. SEG 48.1244)

Di Stefano, G. 2013. Camarina. Le acquisizioni, il museo tematico, la collezione "Biagio Pace", il lapidario. Ispica. At 27-28 dr

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3022. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4387985>